

RESPONSE PAPER**LAST NAME: Abbo Adoum****FIRST NAME: Mahamat****PROGRAM CODE: DSDD****COURSE CODE: ACA - 401D****PERIOD NUMBER: 1****INSTRUCTOR: Dr. Gulma****Edit or delete text to show actual information below:**

The author applied US conventions of grammar, usage, and mechanics.

The author used Turabian (in-text/parenthetical)

The author did use Zotero to insert references

The author did *not* use Grammarly Premium (EUCLID provides access)

The author used the following software: MSWord 2016 on Windows 10

ACADEMIC ESSAY WRITING

1) INTRODUCTION

Writing skills are essential to assure that the written output will be highly and relevant to the reason why the document has been created. An academic essay aims to persuade readers of idea based on evidence (EUCLID 2019, 1) . It is very important to always be aware of the format and content. Although easy writing is not a linear process, some consider it as a burden while others see it as an opportunity to express their thoughts and opinions. When creating an academic writing essay, it is very important to relay a sensible and clear argument to the target. They are some basic steps should be followed and stages to work through several times.

2) DEVELOPPING AN ACADEMIC ESSAY

The first step in academic essay writing is to determine the topic and develop a thesis statement, which is simply a concise statement of essay's main idea by defining the question and analyzing the task. To decide how to answer an essay question, you need to identify what the question requires in term of content and genre. You must know whether you have been asked to argue, analyze, or discuss the topic. There will be times where you also need to compare the items present in your subject or explain the underlying factors that can affect the topic. Questions can be broken down into parts so that can be better understood. It is important to identify key words and phrases in the topic. Key words are the words in an essay that tell the approaches to take when answering the question, they could be a task word which usually verbs and tell what to do to answer the question. Content words tell what the topic area are and help us to focus on the research. In other hand, limiting words narrow abroad topic and indicate aspect to focus on. The content

words help us focus on research and reading on the correct area.” Be sure that understand what the question requires you to do” (ibid.). Understanding exactly what has been asked, analyzing then answering the essay’s is central.

a) Research, reading and Finding the right resources

Once the thesis statement is determined and the questions understood, it is time to draw up an initial essay plan and begin the research. Begin by writing the general subject then write down all the related topic that come to mind based on what you already know. “Work out your initial thoughts and ideas about the topic and write a preliminary essay plan to help guide your research” (ibid.). Since academic essay are widely used in the field of education and research, you need to ensure that your writing is both logical, interesting and informative. The items that are commonly seen in academic essay contain insights, actual occurrences, ideas and facts. Academic essay can only be fully maximized if it can present facts. Primary research maybe helpful a bit more precise review of the research topic can help gather more information that can be helpful in the development of the content.

Always assess the resources of information to ensure they are credible and can be used for support and evidence. When searching for reputable sources, look for academic journal, newspapers, government or organizational website or website writing by some expert and credentials in the topic. In this information age, one source of information often leads to another. In fact, we may find so much information that will be hard to know what to do with it or which one is credible. Though, it is important to find information from reputable source to booster your argument or present accurate information. “An academic essay should include relevant examples, supporting evidence and information from academic texts or credible sources” (ibid).

There are three general sources of information: primary, secondary and tertiary. The primary source is usually a document or result that is being reported firsthand. In other words, primary sources are original resources that not made by someone. Secondary resources values discuss or comment on the primary source. Tertiary resource is a source that summarizes, or compiles fact and knowledge produced by someone else. Tertiary resources are often some kind of assemblage of primary and secondary resources. They are convenient for quick access to summarized facts but not all those sources that belong to this category are considered suitable for academic essay writing. Conducting research is more than just collecting sources. We need to evaluate the quality of source. Always access sources of information to ensure their credibility and refer to evidence, facts, and real data as it can help strengthen the claims.

When considering how to write an academic essay do not wait until the last minute to begin the research. Earlier start gives plenty of time to familiarize with the topic and develop ideas. Once the information is gathered, the next step is to review the sources and take note on the important facts with the question clear in mind (EUCLID 2019, 2). it is vital to write down or save the bibliographic information for all sources. This information includes author’s name, title of the article page numbers, date on which the source was

published. “It is important to take/make notes from your what you read” (ibid.). This will help with referencing as well.

b) Organizing the information, creating outline and writing the essay

After the research has done and ideas are developed, the next step is organizing the idea by creating a second essay plan (ibid.). With this, the academic essay can be more accurate and comprehensive and can also help gather your thoughts first and identify how to put them all together. Each paragraph should focus on one separate idea. Paragraphs can be arranged in numbers of ways, such as chronologically or from least important to most important. “Make sure that paragraphs are arranged in logical sequence”(EUCLID 2019, 4). It is important that the paragraphs flow from one to the next to form a cohesive essay. In addition to helping you stay organized, creating an outline will also help to filter any unnecessary information.

Once the direction is clear and after having done the outline. It is time to create the first draft. A draft essay will help you work out how you will answer the question and which evidence and example you will use, and how the argument will be structure (EUCLID 2019, 2). While thesis provides with paper’s general direction, it will not necessarily provide with a plan for how to organize all the points, large and small. The task of the outline is to find the paper’s “best structure.” “best structure” means the structure that best to support the argument that you intend to make and help to communicate your ideas and answer the question. “All essay should include the following structures: Introduction, body, and conclusion” (EUCLID 2019, 3).

Although, introduction and conclusion are among the most challenging of all paragraphs, they must do more than simply state a topic sentence and offer support. The introduction should include thesis statement with general text and move from general to specific. This text can include background information for your argument to context in which you have approached your examination of the thesis, and how the rest of the essay is organized. When writing a paper about matter that in controversial, begin by summarizing the point of view of your adversaries then state your own position in opposition to theirs. In this way you place yourself clearly in the ongoing conversation.

The body consists of paragraphs and where you present your arguments, answer the question by developing a discussion. “If your question has more than one part, structure the body into sections that deal with each part of the question” (ibid.). Each paragraph should begin with an introduction statement to let the reader know the main point related to the idea. This is where you use the research conducted earlier. You can put fact, statistics or other thoughts to back up the point you are making in each paragraph. Information and idea from others should always provide a citation to acknowledge that the information came from somewhere else, not doing is a plagiarism. Academic institutions have strict policies against plagiarism. “Plagiarism is a serious offense that can have serious consequences” (EUCLID 2019, 4).

The conclusion is also difficult to write, even if the points of the paper are strong. The overall effect of the argument might fall to pieces if the paper as whole is badly concluded. A summary of what the reader has just read is important to the conclusion, but a good conclusion do more than that. The conclusion should move from specific to general. It should summarize or reflect the main idea and emphasize the importance of your contribution to it. Consider again the background information which you begin and return to the key terms and point out how your essay has added new dimension to their meaning. The conclusion should be a final broad statement for the future direction for research but never includes new information.

“Most essays are dramatically improved by careful editing. If possible, put your essay aside for few days before you begin to edit. This gives you time to think further about your answer and argument and return to work with a fresh perspective” (ibid.). You must make large scale changes and check the logic, flow transitions and make changes in the structure and order of the paragraphs. You should make sure that your ideas are fully developed, and all the ideas are supported by credible evidence.

3) CONCLUSION

Writing is always part of the lives of people. May it be students who need to pass academic requirement or employees who are asked to submit a written report. There will always be a reason why people write within the scope of their functions and responsibilities. As a student there will be an instance where we will be required to write an academic essay. I found it difficult myself to write an academic essay but believe that following the steps in ACA-401/ACA-401D COURSEPACK PERIOD 1 provided by EUCLID, I can create an academic essay that is both outstanding and relevant.

If you still do not feel confident in writing your own academic essay from scratch, then you can refer to templates and sample which you can download online. Doing this will allow you to be more familiar with the common content and basic formats that are usually seen in academic essay. When using a template as a guide, always make sure that it is applicable to the study that you are practicing or the academic field or discipline where you will use your academic essay.

REFERENCES

Cleenewerck, Laurent and Kabiru Gulma, 2nd ed. 2019. *ACA-401/ACA-401D Coursepack: Period 1*. Bangui: Central African Republic: Euclid University.

Cleenewerck, Laurent and Kabiru Abubakar Gulma. 2025. ACA-401/ACA 401D Course Pack: Period 1. 6th ed. Washington, D.C.: Euclid University Press. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15245536>.